

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article examines the role and importance of the teacher in foreign language education, their duties and responsibilities. It is emphasized that the teacher is not only a knowledge provider, but also an important person who organizes the educational process, encourages students, and guides them. The article discusses the teacher's communicative, methodological, psychological, and information technology competencies, as well as their personal qualities and professional ethics. It is emphasized that the development of innovative approaches and modern technologies in foreign language education requires new skills from the teacher, making his role more important and complex. The article is intended for foreign language teachers, methodologists, and researchers in the field of pedagogy.

Keywords: teacher, role, tasks, competence, communicative, methodological, psychological, information technologies, personal qualities, professional ethics, innovative approaches, modern technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Today, at a time when globalization processes are intensifying, knowledge of foreign languages is important not only for personal development, but also for ensuring the competitiveness of states in the international arena. Therefore, the main goal of foreign language education is not only to teach language grammar, but also to develop students' communicative competence, that is, the ability to

communicate freely and correctly in a foreign language. The role of a foreign language teacher in achieving this goal is invaluable. A teacher is not only an educator, but also an important person who organizes the educational process, motivates students, and gives them direction. With her professional skills, personal qualities, and love for students, she awakens in their hearts a desire to learn a foreign language.

But the modern world is changing rapidly. The development of innovative approaches and modern technologies also has an impact on foreign language education. This requires new skills from the teacher and makes their role more important and complex. From this point of view, this article aims to analyze the role, tasks, competencies, personal qualities of the teacher in foreign language education and the changes occurring under the influence of modern trends. We hope that this article will help foreign language teachers, methodologists, and researchers in the field of pedagogy to reflect on current issues of foreign language education and improve their activities.

I. The concept of a foreign language teacher and its specific features.

A foreign language teacher is a specialist who teaches students foreign languages. Their main task is to effectively teach students the language, develop their language comprehension and communication skills. Specific features of foreign language teachers are:

Linguistics. A foreign language teacher must have excellent knowledge of the language being taught. For example, they should have a deep understanding of grammatical rules, lexical, and phonetic features in German and Spanish [1, 447].

Pedagogical skills. The teacher must understand the needs of students and choose appropriate teaching methods. This may include methods such as interactive lessons, games, and group work.

Teaching culture. It is important for a foreign language teacher to also teach the culture and traditions of the language they teach. Providing information about

culture, customs, and history in German and Spanish increases students' interest in the language.

Communication skills. The teacher must be able to communicate effectively with students [2, 147]. This includes answering students' questions, encouraging them, and ensuring their active participation in the lesson process.

Innovative approach. The use of modern technologies in the lesson process, for example, the use of online resources, mobile applications, and multimedia materials, is one of the teacher's distinctive features [3, 103].

Individual approach. Each student has their own learning style and pace. The teacher should take these differences into account and implement an individual approach.

Motivation. The teacher should encourage students to learn a foreign language and help them achieve their goals.

A foreign language teacher is an important person who not only teaches the language, but also contributes to the cultural and personal development of students. The role of the teacher in teaching German and Spanish is of particular importance, as these languages have their own unique culture and history. Teachers need to constantly update their knowledge and skills, as well as develop their methods in accordance with the needs of students [4, 151].

II. Roles and responsibilities of a foreign language teacher.

A foreign language teacher is a specialist engaged in teaching students foreign languages, developing their language comprehension and communication skills. On the example of German and Spanish, the duties and responsibilities of a foreign language teacher are:

1. Create a lesson plan. The teacher should develop a lesson plan in accordance with the curriculum. This plan should correspond to the students' level of knowledge, needs, and goals.

2. Selection of teaching methods. The teacher should apply various teaching

methods during the lesson. For example, in teaching German grammar and vocabulary, interactive methods, games, and role-playing games can be used. In the Spanish language, the use of video materials and audio resources can be effective in teaching culture and traditions.

3. Assessment of student knowledge. The teacher must regularly assess students' knowledge and monitor their development. This can be done through tests, written assignments, and oral examinations.

4. Individual approach. Each student has their own learning style and pace. Taking these differences into account, the teacher should implement an individual approach and provide the necessary assistance to the students.

5. Teaching culture. It is important for a foreign language teacher to also teach the culture and traditions of the language they teach. Providing information about culture, customs, and history in German and Spanish increases students' interest in the language.

6. Development of communication skills. The teacher should pay attention to the development of students' communication skills. This is achieved by providing students with various tasks and exercises for the practical application of the language.

7. Motivation and encouragement. The teacher should encourage students to learn a foreign language and help them achieve their goals. This can be done by recognizing students' achievements and offering them additional resources.

8. Use of modern technologies. Applying modern technologies in the lesson process, such as using online resources, mobile applications, and multimedia materials, is one of the teacher's responsibilities [5, 394].

A foreign language teacher is an important person who not only teaches the language, but also contributes to the cultural and personal development of students. The role of the teacher in teaching German and Spanish is of particular importance, since these languages have their own culture and history. Teachers

need to constantly update their knowledge and skills, as well as develop their methods in accordance with the needs of students.

III. Personal qualities of a teacher and their influence

A foreign language teacher must possess a number of personal qualities in order to effectively perform their duties. These qualities strengthen the teacher's influence on students and make the lesson process more effective. Here are the personal qualities that are important for a foreign language teacher and their impact:

When the teacher is patient, students feel comfortable and are ready to ask questions and admit their mistakes. This helps students participate more actively in the learning process. The teacher's positive attitude motivates the students. In a positive environment, students feel free and their interest in learning the language increases. A creative teacher can conduct lessons in an interesting and interactive way. This attracts students' attention and makes the learning process more effective.

The teacher must be able to express their thoughts clearly and understandably, as well as be able to listen to the opinions of students. This ensures effective communication and exchange of ideas during the lesson. It is important for the teacher to understand the students' feelings and approach them accordingly [6, 15]. Empathy helps students feel comfortable and establish trusting relationships between teacher and students.

The teacher must have the ability to effectively plan and organize lessons. This ensures an orderly and effective lesson process. A teacher must constantly update their knowledge and skills. This ensures that the teacher is aware of innovations in their field and offers students the most modern teaching methods. The teacher must adapt to the needs of students and changes in the lesson process. This helps the teacher conduct lessons more effectively [7, 66].

For a foreign language teacher, personal qualities not only determine their professional success, but also have a great influence on the learning process of students. The teacher's patience, positive attitude, creativity, and other qualities

increase students' motivation, strengthen their self-confidence, and make the language learning process more interesting and effective.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the role of the teacher in foreign language education is invaluable. As noted in the article, he is not only an educator, but also an important person who organizes the educational process, motivates students, and guides them. A teacher, with their professional skills, personal qualities, and love for students, awakens in their hearts the desire to learn a foreign language and creates the foundation for them to become successful people in the future.

At the same time, the teacher is required to constantly improve their qualifications, master new methods, and acquire skills in using modern technologies. Because a teacher of the 21st century should not only provide knowledge, but also be a partner of students in the educational process, a person who shows them the way and constantly supports them. It should also be remembered that no matter how important modern technologies and innovative approaches are, they can never be replaced by the human attitude of a teacher. It is this attitude that awakens students' interest in learning a foreign language and plays an important role in their success.

In the future, the role of the teacher in foreign language education will become even more important. Because as globalization processes accelerate, the demand for people who know foreign languages, can freely express their thoughts, and can communicate with different cultures will increase. The selfless work of foreign language teachers is of decisive importance in meeting this demand.

In conclusion, the role of the teacher in foreign language education is incomparable and its place can never be replaced by technologies. A teacher should be a selfless, knowledgeable, and kind person responsible for the development of the future generation.

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